

APPLICATIONS OF OPTOELECTRONIC OSCILLATORS FOR HIGH SPEED CLOCK RECOVERY AND RF SIGNAL DISCRIMINATION

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Introduction

The use of photonic systems to address the demands of high speed signal processing has grown swiftly in the past few years. One current photonic technology that has been extensively researched for analog and digital applications is the Optoelectronic Oscillator, often referred to as an OEO [1]. The OEO was first introduced by Yao and Maleki [2, 3] in 1996 as a source for high frequency, low phase noise signals. Since the OEO provides high performance with the use of commercial parts that are inexpensive, multiple demonstrations have been made both improving and extending the initial design. In fact the OEO has been used for far more than just signal generation. A couple of applications that have received a large amount of attention are clock recovery and signal discrimination. This paper will review the multiple advancements in OEOs for these applications.

OEO for Clock Recovery

An OEO can be locked to an external signal so that the OEO's output is synchronized to the external signal through the process of injection locking. Injection locking an OEO has been used for regenerative mode locking [4], data format conversion [5] and even to suppress non-oscillating modes in either the same OEO [6] or a slave OEO [7, 8]. Other demonstrations used digital data as the injection locking signal in order to use an OEO for clock recovery [9, 10]. Clock recovery can be used to re-time the data, which is one of the "R's" in 3R regenerators used in digital optical networks (with the other two R's represented by re-amplification and re-shape).

Figure 1: (a) Theoretical and (b) measured plot of the phase noise of an injection locked OEO along with the injected signal and free running OEO's phase noise. $\mathcal{L}_{inj}(\omega)$, $\mathcal{L}_{free}(\omega)$, and $\mathcal{L}_{OEO}(\omega)$ are defined as the phase noise for the injected signal, the free-running slave OEO RF signal, and the injection locked OEO oscillator, respectively [1].

The OEO clock recovery performance can be measured by looking at the phase noise of the OEO before and after injection locking. The phase noise of an OEO that is being injection locked by an external signal is shown theoretically in Fig 1(a) and experimentally in Fig 1(b) [1]. Note that the OEO's phase noise follows the phase noise of the injected signal over the locking range and then follows the phase noise of the OEO without any injected signal (free-running). Between the two operating points the phase noise follows a

transfer function given by $P_{transfer}(\omega) = 1 / \left(1 + \left(\frac{2\omega}{\omega_{lock}} \right)^2 \right)$ which has the form of a low-pass filter [1].

OEO for Signal Discrimination

An analog signal processing application using OEOs is signal discrimination in cluttered RF environments. For this, a multimode optoelectronic oscillator for selective amplification of RF signals has been demonstrated [11, 12]. This system works by injecting an RF signal into the OEO cavity, much like in the clock recovery case. However the main differences are the OEO is kept just below its oscillating threshold and the electrical bandpass filter is removed, allowing any cavity mode to potentially oscillate. As seen in Fig. 2, when the injected signal's frequency matches one of the modes of the OEO cavity, the OEO will amplify the signal. If the RF signal's frequency does not match the OEO modes, the signal will see loss. This system can then be used to discriminate between different RF signals based upon their frequency.

Figure 2: RF signal after passing through a multimode OEO. The signal sees gain or loss depending on its frequency.

Conclusion

While the OEO has been around for over 18 years, it continues to see use in many different applications beyond its original intent. Clock recovery and signal discrimination are two applications of the OEO that impact both the digital and analog communities.

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